

Forest change and disturbance type mapping in Bulgaria using Sentinel-2 imagery – potentialities and problems

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Abstract: To face current challenges related with protection and sustainable management of forested territories monitoring is a crucial prerequisite. Remote sensing and satellite missions such as Sentinel-2 in particular are indispensable source of information on forest change that can complement large-area, national-level monitoring systems. Here we present a case study from Bulgaria that evaluated the potential and problems of using a simple analytical approach based on image differencing and machine learning for mapping forest change and identifying the type of forest disturbances. Yearly forest change was mapped with good accuracy (76-85%) based on change detection in several vegetation indices. However, the performance of random forest classification in distinguishing three main disturbance types, Wildfire, Wind/snow/ice, and Insects/pathogens, was inadequate possibly because of a lack of unique spectral signal of these disturbances.

Картографиране на промени и типове повреди в горите в България използвайки изображения от Sentinel-2 – възможности и проблеми

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Резюме: За справянето с настоящите предизвикателства, свързани с опазването и устойчивото управление на залесените територии, мониторингът е решаваща предпоставка. Дистанционното наблюдение и по-специално сателитните мисии като Sentinel-2 са незаменим източник на информация за промените в горите, който може да допълни системите за мониторинг на големи площи, вкл. на национално ниво. Докладът представя пример от България, който оценява потенциала и проблемите при използването на прост аналитичен подход, базиран на разлика на изображения и машинно обучение, за картографиране на промените в горите и идентифициране на вида на повредите в горите. Годишната промяна на гората е картографирана с добра точност (76-85%) въз основа на разлики в стойностите на вегетационни индекса. Въпреки това, ефективността на класификацията чрез метода „random forest“ при разграничаване на три основни вида повреди, горски пожар, вятър/сняг/лед и насекоми/патогени, беше неадекватна, вероятно поради липса на уникален спектрален сигнал при тези повреди.

Introduction

Changes in the extent and condition of forest ecosystems have important economic, societal, and ecological implications, manifesting at different scales, from local to planetary. Forests worldwide are still subject to substantial human pressure due to timber production as well as to various natural disturbances, though variations in the intensity and type of these processes exist between countries and regions [1]. To face these challenges and support sustainable management of forested territories monitoring is a crucial task. Systematic collection of data about forests can also contribute valuable information for understanding our ever-changing environment. For example, the current and future scale

and regime of wildfires, pest infestations and other disturbances need to be monitored in order to assess and predict interactions between different biotic and abiotic factors, and management practices. Analysis of satellite remote sensing imagery was proven as an effective tool for mapping land cover including forest. Therefore, it is now increasingly implemented on an operational basis to support forest monitoring.

Numerous algorithms to derive forest change and disturbance maps based on optical satellite data such as those provided by the Landsat and Sentinel-2 missions have been proposed by the research community in recent years. Detecting change (the focus being mainly on tree cover loss) and mapping various types of disturbances can be regarded as separate objectives although they are closely related and some change detection methods can provide clues for the type of disturbance. A review of change detection in ecosystem monitoring with remote sensing digital imagery was published by Coppin et al. [2]. More recently, Hirschmugl et al. [3] reviewed the methods for mapping forest disturbance and degradation from optical remote sensing data. They divide existing change detection approaches into two main categories: image-to-image change detection and time series analysis.

The image-to-image change detection, also called “bitemporal change detection”, is the most basic change detection approach. It uses a base image acquired at the start of the monitoring period and a second image at the end of the period. The methods in this category are very diverse and include among others: post-classification comparison (e.g. comparing forest/non-forest maps from different periods [4-6]); image differencing (e.g. [7]) or ratioing where using spectral bands or vegetation indices such as NDVI [8], Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR) [9], Disturbance Index (DI) [10-11], etc.; multitemporal classification (e.g. [12]); multitemporal principal component analysis [13], etc.

Time series analysis or trajectory-based analysis [14] are mostly using Landsat Time Series (LTS) data. For example, Zhu et al. [15] proposed the Continuous Monitoring of Forest Disturbance Algorithm (CMFDA) which use every cloud and snow free Landsat image in the year to estimate surface reflectance model for each pixel. The models should be estimated using data from a period without change. The model can predict surface reflectance for pixels at any location and any date assuming persistence of land cover. CMFDA detects forest change by differencing the predicted and observed Landsat images for particular date. Similar approach, based on the BFAST method (Break detection For Additive Season and Trend, [16]) was taken by Verbesselt et al. [17]. It identifies and models stable historical variation in the satellite signal to enable change detection within newly acquired data. Another method using LTS is Vegetation Change Tracker (VCT) [18, 19]. For each pixel and band, a forest z-score (FZ) is calculated based on the means and standard deviations of the spectral values of forest samples. It is a measure of forest likelihood. The Z-scores of different bands can be integrated in a single measure, an integrated forest z-score (IFZ). Based on the distinctive IFZ temporal profiles of different land cover and forest change processes, decision rules are used to identify persisting land cover types and to detect disturbances [19]. Kennedy et al. [20] proposed a method where four hypothesized models of disturbance or recovery are being fit to the data. The model that best fits the data is then found based on the p-value of the f-statistic. The method is based on the recognition that many phenomena associated with changes in land cover have distinctive temporal progressions both before and after the change event, and that these lead to characteristic temporal signatures in spectral space [20]. Similar approach, based on shape-restricted spline fitting algorithm was used in Schroeder et al. [21]. LandTrendr [22] is another method that can be used with yearly LTS. First, the temporal trajectories of spectral variables (e.g. NBR) are extracted on a pixel-by-pixel basis. Then, these trajectories are subject of a temporal segmentation algorithm. It finds a sequence of straight-line segments that capture the broad features of the trajectory. Similar trajectory segmentation method was proposed by Hermosilla et al. [23].

Many remote sensing studies on forest disturbance are focusing on the ability to identify areas affected by a specific disturbance agent, e.g. insects, wildfire, storm, etc. One of the main tasks is to find which spectral bands and VIs are the most useful for distinguishing between disturbed and unaffected forest. For example, it was shown by Abdullah et al. [24] that several VIs calculated from Sentinel-2 have a high potential for mapping changes induced by bark beetle, particularly some red-edge and water-related indices. Similar results were obtained by Foster et al. [25]. The NBR index [9] was found to provide the best distinction between burned and unburned areas. Einzmann et al. [26] evaluated the ability of RapidEye to detect windthrow.

Differences in spectral characteristics of disturbed forest compared with the surrounding undisturbed forest were observed in many studies. However, discerning between different types of forest disturbances may be challenging [27] due to similarity of spectral properties of some disturbance types. Nevertheless, increasing interest in this issue is observed in recent years. For example, Baumann et al. [27] were able to separate windfall disturbance from clear-cut harvesting using Landsat data and support vector machine classifier. Wildfires and clear-cut harvests were mapped in boreal forest using Landsat data by Schroeder et al. [28]. Ranson et al. [29] found good separation of several forest and disturbance classes, including clear-cut and insect damage through the Landsat ETM+ spectral bands. Helmer et

al. [30] mapped four types of forest disturbance in tropical dry forest using a time series of eight Landsat and Advanced Land Imager image mosaics and a decision tree classification. Wilson and Sader [31] used multivariate unsupervised classification to compare NDVI and NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture Index) in their ability to detect forest harvest type. In the study of Hais et al. [32], Landsat TM/ETM+ imagery was used to analyse the spectral response and temporal progress of two types of disturbances of spruce forest (bark beetle outbreak and clear-cuts). A set of metrics derived from a Landsat time series, that characterize the temporal, spectral, and geometrical properties of change objects (groups of contiguous pixels, previously identified as change), were used to attribute these change objects to a change type (i.e., fire, harvesting, road, and non-stand-replacing changes) using a Random Forest (RF) classifier [33]. In a similar study, Huo et al. [34] used RF and features extracted from pixel temporal profile to classify forest disturbance agents (stress, fire, stem removal). Other studies related with disturbance type attribution include [21, 35-38] among others.

Sophisticated methods based on LTS provide accurate results but require long time series (over 10 years) and are suited for retrospective-style analyses. They may not be applicable to the short time series of Sentinel-2. A diversity is observed in the spectral variables used to detect change. While universal variables do not exist it is evident that reflectance in the SWIR part of the spectrum, NBR, DI, and Tasseled Cap indices are preferred in many studies. Finally, differentiating between several types of disturbance remains challenging. Machine learning algorithms, such as RF, are being tested in recent years to solve such types of questions giving promising results.

The aim of this study is to evaluate an approach for forest change and disturbance type mapping in Bulgaria using Sentinel-2 imagery based on simple and well-established methods including image differencing and random forest. Disturbance is here defined to encompass both natural and anthropogenic disturbances.

Data

Atmospherically corrected (level 2A) Sentinel-2 imagery used in this study were available from Google Earth Engine (GEE) [39].

To increase accuracy of wildfire mapping in this study active fire detection data from Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) sensor, on board the Terra and Aqua satellites and from VIIRS (Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite) sensor, on board the NASA/NOAA Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership (SNPP) were used. The spatial resolution of the active fire detection pixel is 1 km and 375 m for MODIS and VIIRS products respectively. MODIS and VIIRS active fire data are provided by the NASA FIRMS (Fire Information for Resource Management System) and were accessed through the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS; <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>; [40]). Data included the period Jan. 2000 – Aug. 2021 and represented vector file containing the centroids of the detection pixels.

Data from the Executive Forest Agency's (ExFA) information system with database of natural forest disturbances in Bulgaria were used as referent dataset. The database includes the date of on-the-field registration of the disturbance by the ExFA staff, the cause, the percent of damaged trees, the code of the subcompartment/s affected, and other data. Disadvantage of the data is that the exact geographic location of the affected forest within the subcompartment is unknown. The data are not readily accessible in GIS as they should be extracted from the database and joined with a vector layer of subcompartment boundaries. We were provided with processed data in vector format for the period from 2016 to August 2021 for the entire country containing an excerpt from the database attributes.

The High Resolution Layer Dominant Leaf Type (HRL-DLT) product provided by the Copernicus programme was used to generate forest/non-forest mask for the study area [41]. We used the 2018 product which has 10 m spatial resolution.

Methods

In order to produce map of forest disturbance types at national level the following workflow was applied. First, a forest change map was produced performing these operations: Sentinel-2 imagery pre-processing; generating temporal composites and vegetation indices; image differencing and generating change map; change map vectorization and extracting spectral features statistics. This part of the workflow was implemented in GEE. Second, a map of forest disturbance types was produced performing these operations: random forest classification; wildfire correction; generating a final disturbance type raster; accuracy assessment. These steps were performed using GEE, Python library Scikit-learn [42], and QGIS. We generated maps for 2019, 2020, and 2021 seasons. A season is defined starting on October 1st of the previous year and ending on September 30th of the current year. For example, the 2019 season started on 1 Oct. 2018 and ended on 30 Sept. 2019. This is because the temporal

composite images used in the algorithm for change detection were composited using data from the months August and September (see below).

Image pre-processing. Image pre-processing included the masking of clouds and cloud shadows based on the information from the Scene Classification band (SCL) which is part of the L2A product [43]. We masked (set as no-data) all pixels where SCL is not one of the following classes: Dark Area Pixels, Vegetation, Not vegetated, Water. For further analysis, only Sentinel-2 bands B2 to B8, B11, and B12 [44] were considered.

Generating temporal composites and vegetation indices. Four temporal composite (TC) images were produced for 2018, 2019, 2020, and 2021 respectively. For that purpose, all Sentinel-2 images with less than 20% cloud cover acquired between August 1st and September 30th of the corresponding year were used. For each pixel, the composite value represents a set percentile of the available observations. Usually the 50th percentile, i.e. the median is used (e.g. [45]), but we also tested other values and selected, based on a visual inspection, the one that best eliminated residual clouds (i.e. clouds not masked in the previous step).

For each TC a quality mask was generated based on the assumption that the TC quality depends on the number of available observations within the compositing period. Therefore, the per-pixel number of available observations was calculated. We considered the TC to be of low quality in areas where lower than 3 observations were available, and these areas were masked.

The following VIs were calculated using the TC images: Normalized Burn Ratio, $NBR=(B8-B12)/(B8+B12)$ [9]; Tasseled Cap Brightness (TCB), Greenness (TCG), and Wetness (TCW) [46-48]; Green ratio, $GR=B8/B3$ [49]; Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, $NDVI=(B8-B4)/(B8+B4)$ [50]; Normalized Difference Infrared Index, $NDII=(B8-B11)/(B8+B11)$ [51]; and Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index, $MSAVI=(2*B8+1-((2*B8+1)^2-8*(B8-B4))^0.5)/2$ [52]. These VIs and the Sentinel-2 bands are further referred to as Spectral Features (SFs) for brevity.

Image differencing. Image differencing is a change detection method [53] where one image is subtracted from another image pixel-by-pixel. We performed the procedure with all SFs by subtracting data of 2019 from 2018, 2020 from 2019, and 2021 from 2020. The resulting “difference” spectral features (dSFs) are denoted by “d”, for example dB2, dNDVI, etc. Non-forest areas were masked out from the difference images based on the HRL-DLT product.

The separability of different forest disturbance types relative to undisturbed forest was analyzed for different dSFs in order to select the most useful dSFs to be used in the next steps of the analysis. This selection was also needed to reduce the computational effort and prevent using redundant data. For this aim a reference dataset consisting of 205 polygons representing undisturbed forest and 205 polygons representing different types of forest disturbance (*Insects/pathogens*, *Wildfire*, *Wind/snow/ice*, and *Harvesting*) was used. The polygons were digitized in GIS using reference data from ExFA’s database complemented with visual interpretation of high resolution images from *Google Earth* and Sentinel-2 images from the *Sentinel Playground* website [54]. The average value of pixels within each polygon was calculated for the dSFs and the data was summarized in the form of box plots. The highest separability of disturbed and undisturbed forest was observed with B4, B12, NDVI, NBR, and TCW (see the results section) and these were selected for the next steps of the change detection algorithm.

The dSF depict spectral differences that could be caused by: forest disturbance events with various intensity, noise introduced by the compositing and cloud/cloud shadow masking algorithms, seasonal effects on vegetation, and subtle inter-annual variations that are not related with forest disturbance events. It is therefore needed to determine forest areas experiencing change due to disturbance based on the assumption that forest disturbance will cause larger spectral difference from one year to the next compared with the other factors. Each of the selected dSFs was transformed into a binary change/no-change map using a threshold. As a rule, the density plot of dSF will be more or less symmetrical and bell-shaped. Pixels clustered around the mean represent unchanged forest while changed pixels occupy the extremes of the distribution. As only forest degradation is relevant for this study, we ignored the potential changes caused by improved forest conditions. Hence, we considered only one extremity of the distribution as being ‘change’; for dB4 and dB12 this is the lower end (or the left side of the density plot) while for dNDVI, dNBR, and dTCW this is the higher end (or the right side of the density plot). A threshold separating change from unchanged pixels can be defined as:

$$\text{threshold} = \text{mean} + n * \text{standard deviation}$$

or

$$\text{threshold} = \text{mean} - n * \text{standard deviation.}$$

The values of the mean and standard deviation used in the above formulas were calculated for each dSF and year using all forested pixels for the territory of Bulgaria. The value of n can be determined by try and error so that the accuracy of the resulting binary map is highest. A range of values between

1 and 4 with 0.25 step increments were tested to find a suitable n value. The accuracy of binary maps resulting from applying different values of n were estimated using a stratified random sample; separate samples for each combination of dSF and year were used. The stratification was based on a reclassified version of the respective dSF where 8 strata were defined with thresholds being 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, and 4 standard deviations from the mean. Ten random points were placed in each stratum. The reference classification of points to either *Forest disturbance* or *Unchanged forest* was performed by visual interpretation of high resolution images from *Google Earth* and Sentinel-2 images from the *Sentinel Playground* website [54]. Points that were found to be non-forest during the visual interpretation (i.e. errors in the HRL-DLT product) were removed. A confusion matrix like this shown in Table 1 was constructed from the sampled data.

Table 1. Example of a confusion matrix ([55], with modifications)

		Reference	
		Unchanged forest	Forest disturbance
dSF binary map	Unchanged forest	True negative (Tn)	False negative (Fn)
	Forest disturbance	False positive (Fp)	True positive (Tp)

The confusion matrix is the basis for accuracy assessment and allows calculation of different accuracy metrics. We used the metrics presented in Havašová et al. [55], namely the kappa index of agreement [56] and the metrics of receiver operating characteristics (ROCs) [57]. In practice, even randomly assigning pixels to either *Forest disturbance* or *Unchanged forest* will produce a map that may have at least some degree of agreement with the reference data just by chance. The kappa index is a measure of how better the examined mapping method from such a random classifier is. Higher kappa index indicates better accuracy. The second method involves constructing a ROC graph, where on the x axis is shown the probability of false positives, P(Fp), and on the y axis is shown the probability of true positives, P(Tp) (Fig.1a). Using the notation from Table 1, the above probabilities are calculated as follows [55]:

$$P(Fp) = Fp / (Tn + Fp)$$

$$P(Tp) = Tp / (Fn + Tp)$$

Each of the tested n values is represented as a point in the ROC space (Fig. 1a). The best n value is the one with the minimal Euclidean distance from a hypothetical, optimal point, where P(Fp) = 0, and P(Tp) = 1 [55]. Euclidean distance is plotted against the tested n values to summarize the results (example shown in Fig. 1b). Thresholds were determined for each season and dSF and also an average, multi-season thresholds were calculated.

Fig. 1. Examples of ROC graph (a) and Euclidean distance graph (b) (data for dTCW and 2021). n: number of standard deviations from the mean.

To prepare a final change/no-change map for each season we combined the change/no-change maps derived from the five dSFs: dB4, dB12, dNDVI, dNBR, and dTCW. At a per-pixel basis, the five input maps may not always agree so it is needed to decide on a rule to resolve such conflicts. We tested four aggregation rules:

- Any – a pixel is marked as a change if it is a change in at least one of the five input maps (least restrictive rule);
- Most – a pixel is marked as a change if it is a change in most (i.e. 3 or more) of the five input maps;
- Most or NBR – a pixel is marked as a change if it is a change in most (i.e. 3 or more) of the five input maps or in the dNBR-derived map;
- All – a pixel is marked as a change only if it is a change in all of the five input maps (the most restrictive rule).

It was also tested what was the effect of using the season-specific thresholds versus those averaged over the three seasons on the final map accuracy. The procedure for accuracy assessment was the same as presented above except that three new stratified random samples were used – one for each season. Three strata were defined: 1) areas which are no-change in all five input maps (with 100 random points); 2) areas which are change in at least one of the five input maps but not in all of them (with 50 random points); and 3) areas which are change in all of the five input maps (50 random points).

Change map vectorization and extracting SF statistics. Groups of contiguous pixels designated as “change” in the forest change map are regarded as “change-patches”. Each “change-patch” is likely the result of a single forest disturbance event. Therefore, it is more sensible to determine the type of disturbance at patch (or “object”) level rather than at pixel level. For this reason, a polygon vector layer was created by vectorising the “change-patches” where each patch gets a unique ID. In order to be classified in the next step these polygons should contain the SFs as attributes. These include the selected five Sentinel-2 bands and VIs from the current and the previous year. Mean values for these SFs are calculated for each polygon and stored as attributes in the vector layer.

Random forest classification. The Random Forest (RF) classification method was used to attribute the polygons from the vector generated in the previous step (i.e. the “change-patches”) to one of three natural disturbance classes: *Wildfire disturbance*, *Wind/snow/ice disturbance*, and *Insects/pathogens disturbance*. Basically, the RF classification is an ensemble method that uses a number of decision tree classifiers where each tree estimates the probabilities (p) of a data point being class i [58]. The final predicted class is the one with highest mean probability estimate across the trees [42].

We used the reference polygons described in the *Image differencing* section to generate training data for the RF classifier. As the three types of disturbance do not include all possible natural disturbance agents we decided to allow for unclassified polygons in the classifications assuming that these include all other types of disturbances and harvesting. The reference polygons from the three seasons were combined (113 in total). Individual pixels at 20 m resolution were sampled within these polygons to generate training data. For each sampled pixel, an ID was assigned corresponding to the ID of the reference polygon in which the pixel falls. Thus, data points coming from the same reference polygon could be identified and grouped together. Values of the five selected SFs were extracted for the year of disturbance and the pre-disturbance year to be used as predictors in the classification. We also tested dSFs as predictors but this resulted in lower accuracy. The parameters of the RF algorithm were tuned using a random grid search. The parameters and the tested values are shown in Table 2. We used grouped 5 Fold cross-validation for the parameter tuning where groups were the IDs. A total of 1523 pixels (data points) were used for the training of the RF model.

The trained RF classifier was used to predict the disturbance type for the vectorised “change-patches” for each season. For each patch, an uncertainty indicator was also calculated representing the ratio between the probability of the class with the second highest probability and the probability of the class with highest probability. The values of this indicator range between 0 (high confidence attributions) and 1 (low confidence attributions). It was used to avoid attributing a patch to a class when the confidence is low [33]. Instead, these patches were treated as unclassified and were labelled as *Other disturbance or uncertain* class. The threshold value used was 0.10.

Table 2. Parameters of the RF algorithm which were tuned and the values tested. Fifty randomly sampled combinations of parameter values were generated for each of five cross-validation folds.

Parameter name	Description	Distribution
n_estimators	Number of trees	100, 200, 300,.....,1000
max_features	Number of features to consider at every split	1, 2, 3, 4, 5
min_samples_split	Minimum number of samples required to split a node	2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30
min_samples_leaf	Minimum number of samples required at each leaf node	1, 2, 3, 4

Wildfire correction. The EFFIS data was used to refine classification results for the *Wildfire disturbance* class. For this purpose, a buffer of 187.5 m and 500 m was generated around VIIRS and MODIS points respectively to form circle with diameter corresponding to the spatial resolution of the original active fire raster products of the two sensors. If a polygon intersected with a buffered active fire detection from the same season, it was marked as *Wildfire disturbance* even if not classified as such by the RF classifier.

Generating a final disturbance type raster. Finally, a disturbance type raster with 10 m resolution is generated. To prepare the final raster first the vector with the classified patches was rasterized and then

combined with the forest change map to include the unchanged forest, non-forest areas and no-data pixels (e.g. areas with poor TC quality).

Accuracy assessment. Stratified random sampling was used to assess the accuracy of the disturbance type maps. The assessment was performed for 2019 and 2021. 100 points were distributed in each of the class *Wildfire disturbance*, *Wind/snow/ice disturbance*, *Insects/pathogens disturbance*, *Other disturbance or uncertain*, and *Forest not changed*. Points that fall within non-forest areas (this is possible because of errors in the HRL-DLT dataset used as a forest mask) are removed from the sample (aprox. 16% of the points in both seasons). Reference labels for the samples were determined through visual interpretation of Sentinel-2 and high resolution images from *Google Earth*, as well as by auxiliary data, including MODIS and VIIRS active fire data and data from the ExFA database of natural forest disturbances. The sampled data were used to calculate the overall accuracy, i.e. the percentage of correctly classified points in the sample. The same data were also used to assess the accuracy of the forest change maps through pooling the points from the different disturbance type classes into a single class. Thus, two classes were only evaluated, *Forest change* and *Forest not changed*.

Results and Discussion

Temporal composites. The selection of the percentile value had a significant effect on the TC (Fig. 2), especially when cloud/cloud shadows were not perfectly masked. The higher values tend to “expose” more of the cloudy pixels left unmasked and the lower values tend to “expose” more of the residual shadow pixels. The median [45] or a slightly lower value is usually recommended to minimize the effects of clouds. The 40th percentile provides for good results according to our tests and was applied for generating the TC images.

The number of observations available for compositing varied between region and year. Fig. 3 shows their distribution for 2018 as an example. More observations, up to 21, were available for the zones of overlap between Sentinel-2 image swaths and the lowlands while in mountainous regions of western Bulgaria less than three observations were available. In the change detection procedure, two TC images are used and therefore the low quality TC mask are combined in the resulting change map. In our case, 2019 season was characterized with the largest number of masked pixels, while for the other two seasons their number was very low.

Fig. 2. Comparison of temporal composite images generated by using different percentile value

Fig. 3. Number of good (cloud and shadow free) observations for the period August-September 2018 over Bulgaria. The outlines of the Sentinel-2 tiles are shown in gray. The white dotted lines show the Sentinel-2 orbit ground tracks.

Selection of SFs. The box plots of dSFs for different disturbance types and non-disturbed forest are shown in Fig. 4. The figure presents the pooled data from the three seasons. From the visible bands of Sentinel-2 most useful are the blue (B2) and the red (B4) band. In both bands, disturbance, regardless of the type, leads to increase in reflectance (in the general case) and thus disturbed areas have negative values in the pre-minus-post disturbance difference image. The green band (B3) is useful for detecting harvesting and wind/snow/ice-related disturbance but the other two disturbance types tend to have dB3 values centered around zero meaning they could not be separated from unchanged forest. The red-edge band B5 showed a similar pattern as B3. The other two red-edge bands, B6 and B7, are not suitable for forest disturbance detection according to our dataset. For most disturbance types (except wildfire) there is no clear pattern in the change of reflectance in these bands after disturbance and it can either increase or decrease depending on the site. The same was observed for the near-infrared band B8. Wildfire-affected forests tend to experience a decrease in reflectance in bands B6, B7, and B8. However, as the other disturbance types are difficult to distinguish from unchanged forest, these bands are not suitable for general change detection. The short-wave infrared bands B11 and B12 provide relatively good separation of disturbed and undisturbed forest. The difference values in these bands are negative for all disturbance types. This is due to increasing reflectance as a result of disturbance. Wildfires are better distinguished in B12 than B11.

As a whole, the Green Ratio (GR) index decreases after forest disturbance. Therefore, the values of the dGR are positive over disturbed areas. The index seems to be useful for detecting forest disturbance caused by harvesting, wildfire, and wind/snow/ice. The next group of indices, including Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Infrared Index (NDII), Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR), and Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI) allowed for relatively good separation between the analyzed classes. Of these, MSAVI appears to be less useful than the other three indices. As with GR, the values of these indices decrease after forest disturbance in the general case. The last group of indices includes the Tasseled Cap Brightness (TCB), Greenness (TCG), and Wetness (TCW). Our dataset shows that the direction of change in TCB depends on the disturbance type; in most cases wildfire leads to decrease, while harvesting and wind/snow/ice disturbances lead to increase. Insects/Pathogens disturbance is practically indistinguishable from undisturbed forest based on the dTCB values. The index is therefore not well suited for general change detection in forests. The other two Tasseled Cap indices are more promising, especially TCW. Both of them decrease after disturbance (regardless of its type), at least in the majority of the reference polygons. The dTCW for not disturbed forest has narrower range than dTCG, which indicates that this index is more stable and less affected by noise and other factors not related with the forest condition. The analysis on relative performance of SFs is based on the pooled dataset but the conclusions apply for the individual seasons as well (data not shown). As mentioned in the *Methods* section B4, B12, NDVI, NBR, and TCW were selected for the next steps of the change detection algorithm.

Fig. 4. Box plots of difference Spectral Features (dSFs) for undisturbed and several types of disturbed forest. For better readability, dSFs with similar ranges are grouped together.

Thresholds determination and aggregated forest change maps. The kappa index and Euclidean distance for different values of n are shown in Fig.5 for all dSFs and seasons. In most cases (10 out of 15) the kappa index and Euclidean distance agree on which n is the best. Usually this is a value between 2 and 3 standard deviations from the mean. When the two metrics disagree the kappa index suggests a higher n (i.e. more restrictive threshold) than the Euclidean distance (between 3 and 4 standard deviations from the mean). We consider such higher values more as an exception. Hence, in case of disagreement between the two metrics the Euclidean distance was preferred.

In addition to providing information for selecting the best n value for the threshold calculation, the plots in Fig. 5 also show that there is difference in performance between dSFs and seasons. In the general case, dNDVI performed worse (i.e. having highest Euclidean distance and lowest kappa) and the accuracy for the 2021 (blue line in the plots) was highest.

Fig. 5. Euclidean distance (left column) and kappa index (right column) as a function of n (the number of standard deviations from the difference spectral feature's (dSF) mean) used to separate *Forest disturbance* from *Unchanged forest*

More importantly, for the same dSF the best n value may differ between seasons. As a result, the calculated threshold value differed as well (Table 3). Table 3 presents the final calculated thresholds by feature and season as well as the averaged, multi-season thresholds.

Table 3. Optimal threshold values for separating *Forest disturbance* from *Unchanged forest*

	Difference Spectral Feature				
	dB4	dB12	dNDVI	dNBR	dTCW
2018-2019	-0.0184	-0.0236	0.1587	0.1441	0.0395
2019-2020	-0.0160	-0.0208	0.1093	0.1724	0.0418
2020-2021	-0.0185	-0.0229	0.1022	0.1147	0.0340
Average	-0.0176	-0.0224	0.1234	0.1437	0.0384

Comparison of accuracy for the four aggregation rules is shown in Fig. 6. It can be concluded that the "Most" and the "Most or NBR" aggregation rules produced more accurate results. No clear preference could be given to any of the two based on these data so we chose "Most" as this method is

more simple. As expected, the application of season-specific thresholds resulted in better accuracy than the application of average thresholds. Therefore, the maps were generated using the season-specific thresholds.

Fig. 6. Euclidean distance (a) and kappa index (b) as a function of the aggregation rule. Low Euclidean distance and high kappa represent higher accuracy.

Accuracy of the maps and discussion. The overall accuracy of the 2019 and 2021 disturbance type maps was insufficient (46% and 51% respectively). The overall accuracy of the change maps was much higher (76% and 85% for 2019 and 2021 respectively). Therefore, the presented simple workflow was effective in its first part i.e. to detect changes in the forest, but failed in the second, i.e. to classify those changes according to the disturbance type. The image differencing method was able to identify reliably changes in forest extent and condition between years. While not explicitly tested, we assume that the usage of a combination of five spectral bands and VIs, instead of a single spectral feature, had a positive effect on accuracy. We used state-of-the-art machine learning method, random forest, and conducted thorough parameter tuning in an attempt to distinguish between the types of disturbance. However, the classification relied only on spectral data, bands and VIs, from the pre and post disturbance TCs. As seen in Fig. 4, different disturbances may not be clearly separable in this data. This is therefore an intrinsically difficult classification problem and other types of data need to be incorporated to enhance separability and improve predictions. These may include MODIS and VIIRS active fire data (in our case they were used for post-processing, not as an input to the classification), data about extreme weather events, topography-related variables, tree species or forest type (coniferous, broadleaved), field observations from the ExFA disturbance database, harvesting operations data, etc. The importance of the auxiliary data was demonstrated in this study, where MODIS/VIIRS hot spot data proved very effective for correcting errors in wildfire classification. It is also important to recognise that disturbance events occur throughout the year and the place may (partly) recover or be cleared shortly after. Thus, a single snapshot approach such as the used here may miss some events or fail to observe their initial cause or intensity. This is particularly true for insects and pathogens, which may have specific seasonal cycle of manifestation. Pathogens-related disturbances may be particularly difficult to detect when only moderate defoliation and/or yellowing is present. Other problem is that infection usually develops within several years and shows seasonality dependant on the type of the pathogen. Note that we trained the classifier with combined data from the three seasons because we wanted to test the possibility to use a single pre-trained classifier (this would be useful in an operational situation). The insufficient number of training data also led to this decision. This approach is convenient (and in our case necessary) but comes at the expense of reduced accuracy because phenological and other inter-annual variations are introduced in the training data. In general, we expect that some improvement in the results may be achieved if more training data are available.

Fig. 7 shows the map of forest disturbance type for 2021 over Bulgaria and some close looks on forest areas affected by different types of disturbance. Fig. 8 to Fig. 11 show additional examples from the three seasons depicting some typical situations and problems with the mapping accuracy. A few main conclusions are drawn from the visual inspection of the maps and summarized as follows:

- In the general case, the proposed algorithm was able to detect forest disturbances leading to complete or significant loss of trees (such as crown wildfires in conifers, clear-cuts, etc.). However, more subtle changes such as those caused by insects and pathogens were frequently missed (Fig. 8(A)). Ground fires in broadleaved forest, characteristic for leaf-off months in some parts of Bulgaria, remain undetected. We tried to detect both high and low intensity changes in one mapping product but it may be more appropriate to set a quantitative criterion for disturbance intensity.
- True wildfires are correctly recognized as such (Fig. 9) but some other disturbances are incorrectly classified as wildfires (Fig. 7(B) and Fig. 10(A)). We found that this most often happened when some broadleaved forests experience premature senescence, possibly due to drought (see next point).

Fig. 7. Forest disturbance type map for 2021. The excerpts show: A) snow/ice induced disturbance in January 2021; B) drying oriental hornbeam forest (August-September 2021) possibly affected by drought (partly misidentified as wildfire); C) and D) wildfires from August and July 2021 respectively; E) forest harvesting (patch cutting).

Fig. 8. Excerpts from the disturbance type map over two coniferous forest plantations (A and B) affected by pathogens and corresponding Sentinel-2 (S2) and high resolution images from *Google Earth* (GE) before and after the events. The full extent of the affected area in (A) was not captured on the map. Part of the affected stand in (B) has been logged and was depicted as class *Other disturbance or uncertain*.

Fig. 9. Excerpts from the disturbance type maps over two areas (A and B) affected by wildfire and corresponding Sentinel-2 (S2) and high resolution images from *Google Earth* (GE) before and after the events.

Fig. 10. Excerpts from the disturbance type maps over two black locust forests (A and B) experiencing inter-annual phenology changes (possibly due to drought) and corresponding Sentinel-2 (S2) images before and after the events

Fig. 11. Excerpts from the disturbance type map over three areas (A, B, and C) affected by snow/ice disturbance in January 2021 and corresponding Sentinel-2 (S2) and high resolution images from *Google Earth* (GE) before and after the event. The affected stands in (C) were cleared within the season and are identified as class *Other disturbance or uncertain*.

- In some places, we observed characteristic inter-annual changes in the colour appearance of forest on the Sentinel-2 images (Fig. 7(B) and Fig. 10) which could not be readily attributed to disturbance. Moreover, no disturbance events were recorded in these territories according to the ExFA forest disturbance database. As they were observed in August and September, we consider these changes as a premature senescence, possibly due to drought, but other factors may be at work as well. As the reason for such changes was not known, they were not considered explicitly in the classification process.
- Snow/ice induced disturbances were observed in many mountain areas in western Bulgaria in January 2021. The affected areas were identified and correctly classified in most cases. However, the class *Wind/snow/ice disturbance* was wrongly assigned to some areas which were logged. The effect of ice breakage on the spectral signal may resemble this of tree cutting as in both cases canopy density is reduced and understorey is exposed.

- It is common forestry practice to clear-cut stands affected by windthrow or pathogens within several weeks in order to prevent infestations and utilize the timber. At the time of the TC image therefore the territory may have been already cleared and classified as *Other disturbance or uncertain* thus preventing the initial disturbance of being detected (Fig. 11(C) and Fig. 8(B)).

Conclusions

We evaluated a simple approach for forest change detection and disturbance type mapping based on easy-to-implement and well-established methods. The image differencing method enabled us to map yearly changes in forest with reasonable accuracy. On the other hand, the random forest classifier was not able to discriminate three major disturbance categories based on spectral bands and VIs. Our results prove that disturbance type mapping with classical earth observation techniques such as supervised spectral classification is a challenging task. Using auxiliary data in the prediction models, including meteorological, active fire, and forestry data may provide a solution. Nevertheless, the change detection maps (binary maps of change versus no-change) presented in this study may be of practical use for Bulgarian institutions because they provide high resolution (10 m), spatially explicit, national level information rapidly and at low-cost.

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